

MONEY SUPPLY AND STOCK MARKET PRICES IN NIGERIA

¹Opara Godstime Ikechukwu, ^{*2}Ogu Callistus and ³Ojinnaka Henry Chigozie

Department of Economics, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria

Email: callistusogu@imsuonline.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17661285>

Key words: Money Supply, Stock Market Prices, Monetary Policy Rate, Liquidity Ratio, Cash Reserve Ratio, All- Share Index, ARDL, Nigeria.	Abstract: <i>This study examined the effect of money supply on stock market prices in Nigeria between 1990 and 2023. The objectives of the study were to determine the extent to which broad money supply (M2), monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio have affected All-Share Index (ALSI) in the Nigerian stock market. Data on the aforementioned variables were collected from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin for various years. Adopting the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to data analysis, the study revealed that lagged ALSI and monetary policy rate have direct effects on current period ALSI while cash reserve ratio, liquidity ratio and money supply (M2) have inverse influences on current period ALSI. However, lagged ALSI, cash reserve ratio and liquidity ratio were statistically significant. The study further revealed a long run relationship between the variables with an adjustment capacity of about 58.5% in event of disequilibrium per annum. The study thus concluded that money supply has a negative insignificant effect on stock market prices in Nigeria. On this backdrop it was suggested amongst other things that drastic measures should be adopted in order to ensure that the volume of money outside the banking system is significantly reduced in order for monetary policies to be more effective in Nigeria. Secondly, deposit money banks should be encouraged to offer competitive deposit rates that will attract more funds into the banking system. Thirdly, there is need for the Central Bank of Nigeria to offer better and competitive rates for treasury bills and other money market instruments in order to keep funds in the banking system.</i>
---	--

1.1 Introduction

The capital market is otherwise known as a stock market. It is a major segment of the financial

market. It is a market where medium and long term stocks are traded. Trading in this market is done via the buying and selling of stocks like

Opara Godstime Ikechukwu, *Ogu Callistus and Ojinnaka Henry Chigozie

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

shares, bonds and debentures. The major stocks traded in the Nigerian capital market are government securities, corporate bonds, ETFs (Exchange Traded Funds) and equities. The equities market is the most popular in Nigeria because being an equity holder makes one a part-owner of a company. According to Donwa and Odia, (2017), for equity holders, returns on equities are by way of price appreciation, scrip issue or dividend payment. In essence, equity holders are entitled to capital gains, additional or bonus shares and regular income. Capital gain arises when a company's stock price increases over time and shareholders can sell their shares at a higher price, thereby earning profit. The issue of bonus shares comes up when a company issues additional shares to existing shareholders without requiring payment. The regular income of equity holders is the portion of the profits of a company that is distributed to shareholders as owners of the company. However, for arbitrageurs, capital gain is the major driving force for investing in the equities market. These investors are constantly switching between markets looking for cheaper stocks to buy while being willing to selling their existing stocks when price appreciates. Thus, they constantly monitor the price movement of stocks on daily basis in the stock market. They equally monitor the All Share Index of various markets as it also reflects movement in the price of shares.

However, movement in the price of stocks of a country is tied to factors like the monetary policy

directives of the monetary authority of that country. Monetary policy is an economic stability weapon that targets the money supply of a country. It affects the price, volume, supply and direction of money. When the money supply is higher than the stipulated level, a contracting monetary policy is implemented and vice versa. In Nigeria, so many measures of monetary policy have been adopted since the establishment of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). These measures or instruments of monetary policy are generally tools available to the CBN which they can use to influence the supply of money in the Nigerian economy. According to Bassey and Ekong (2019), these measures include: moral suasion, discount and interest rate policy, open market operations, legal reserve requirements (cash reserve ratio and liquid asset ratio), special deposits, aggregate credit ceiling, credit discrimination in favour of indigenes, selective credit control, and control of non-bank financial institution. However, it must be stated that the popular instruments of monetary policy used in Nigeria today are monetary policy rate (MPR), cash reserve ratio and liquidity ratio. Monetary policy rate is regarded as the mother of all rates as it directly affects the lending and deposit rates of banks which should have a bearing on money supply. Cash reserve ratio is a primary reserve while liquidity ratio is a secondary reserve. Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) are expected to maintain these reserves with the apex bank for liquidity management and other purposes.

Opara Godstime Ikechukwu, *Ogu Callistus and Ojinnaka Henry Chigozie

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

Generally, if the apex bank wants to contract economic activities, they increase the MPR, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio. The converse is the case when they want to expand economic activities. These actions have direct effects on the money supply of the country. Money supply (M2) here entails the aggregation of currency in circulation and banks deposits (demand deposits and time deposits). Thus, the workability of monetary policy is tied to the operations of Deposit Money Banks. Since bank deposit is a major component of money supply, it is the belief of the monetary authorities that altering the ability of banks to create deposits will directly affect the money supply of the country. As such, increasing monetary policy rate will increase lending rate which will discourage customers from borrowing from the banks and vice versa. Also, increasing cash reserve ratio or liquidity ratio will reduce the loanable funds of banks. Given this shortage, lending becomes more expensive and this reduces the credit creation ability of banks and vice versa.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In examining the cause-effect nexus between money supply and stock market prices, researchers have adopted different approaches with respect to variables adopted, time scope, research design and analytical tools employed. However, most of these studies were done in countries like Sweden (Eriksson & Harja, 2023); Mauritius, England, Trinidad and Tobago,

Australia and Japan (Bissoon, Seetanah, Bhattu-Babajee, Gopy-Ramdhany & Seetah, 2016); Japan (Hirota, 2023); Czech Republic (Pícha, 2017). This makes studies that focused on Nigeria scarce in the literature. However, with respect to money supply and stock market prices in Nigeria, Ogbonna (2021) adopted a simple regression model where stock market capitalization was regressed on broad money supply. A simple regression model is considered inadequate in estimating the relationship between variables. Moving a step further, in a recent study, Udeorah, Oladosu and Odiche (2025) adopted a multiple regression model whereby market capitalization was regressed on interest rate, broad money supply, liquidity ratio and exchange rate. Market capitalization is not a good measure of stock market prices. John and Ezeabasili (2020) considered Nigeria, Ghana and South Africa but the model adopted was inadequate as they focused on All Share Index and broad money supply.

Given the foregoing, there seem to be a dearth of current studies that adopted an adequate multiple regression models that depicts the relationship between money supply and stock market prices in Nigeria. On the basis of the above identified gaps, this study was undertaken.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of money supply on stock market prices in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

1. Determine the extent to which broad money supply has affected the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the stock market in Nigeria;
2. Examine the effect of monetary policy rate on the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the Nigerian stock market;
3. Ascertain the effect of liquidity ratio on stock market's All-Share Index (ALSI) in Nigeria; and
4. Investigate the relationship between cash reserve ratio and the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the stock market in Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

1. To what extent has broad money supply affected the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the stock market in Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of monetary policy rate on the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the Nigerian stock market?
3. What is the effect of liquidity ratio on stock market's All-Share Index (ALSI) in Nigeria?
4. What is the relationship between cash reserve ratio and the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the stock market in Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: Broad money supply has not significantly affected the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the stock market in Nigeria

Ho₂: Monetary policy rate has an insignificant effect on the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the Nigerian stock market;

Ho₃: Liquidity ratio has no significant effect on stock market's All-Share Index (ALSI) in Nigeria.

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between cash reserve ratio and the All-Share Index (ALSI) of the stock market in Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Money Supply

One of the major targets of every monetary policy is to control the level of money supply in an economy. This is because the supply of money has a direct effect on inflation rate and interest rate (Otalú, 2014). So to achieve price stability, monetary authorities through monetary policy try to control money supply. Accordingly, a nation's money supply is determined by the monetary policy actions taken by its central bank. Thus, money supply denotes the total value of money in an economy and it comprises of currency (notes and coins) and deposits with commercial banks (Deposit Money Banks) (Otalú, 2014). There are basically two types of money supply in Nigeria; namely narrow money M1 and broad money M2. M1 measure of money supply comprises currency outside banks and demand deposits (current accounts) at the banks and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), while M2 includes M1, savings, time and foreign currency deposits (Yahaya & Lamidi, 2015). The component of savings, time and external currency deposits are also called quasi-money. M2 measure of money supply comprises of the total liquidity in the economy. When the levels of

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

money supply by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) changes, it changes through the control of the base money. The Base money includes currency and coins outside the banking system and the deposits of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) held by the central bank. If the central bank observes that prices are rising and there is too much money in circulation, it may reduce the base money by decreasing money supply. To reduce the base money, the CBN sells financial securities to banks and the non-bank public so as to reduce the money creation ability of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) and vice versa (Ibeabuchi, 2017).

2.1.2 Monetary Policy Rate

Monetary policy rate is a major monetary policy tool. It is also called bank rate, discount rate, variable rediscount rate or minimum rediscount rate. According to Alalade, Oseni and Adekunle (2020), it is the rate at which the central bank of a country rediscounts bills of exchange presented by Deposit Money Banks. It is as such the standard rate at which the apex bank is prepared to buy or rediscount bills of exchange or other commercial papers eligible for purchase. Thus, monetary policy rate is a short term anchor rate designed to influence other money market rates. It is usually fixed to promote policy efficiency. In Nigeria, the MPR is set by the Monetary Policy Committee (MPC) to guide the short term rates and correct any imbalances that arise from monetary under or over supply to the overall economy (CBN, 2023). Put differently,

discount rate refers to the minimum rate at which the Central Bank stands ready to advance loans or discount bills to the banking system. In the words of Nnanna (2021), “what happens with discount rate is that when DMBs are faced with a shortage of cash reserves, they approach the central bank to get their bills of exchange rediscounted. It is a common method of borrowing by DMBs from the apex bank. The central bank rediscounts the bills presented by the banks because it is a part of its function as lenders of last resort”.

2.1.3 Cash Reserve Ratio

Cash reserve ratio is otherwise known as primary reserve. It is an instrument that aims at ensuring a high level of liquidity in banks. This ratio represents the minimum amount of cash deposits to be maintained by Deposit Money Banks with the central bank. The ratio expresses the relationship between cash deposits to the total deposit liabilities, certificates of deposits, and promissory notes held by the non-bank public (Ojima & Ajudua, 2024). According to Udeh (2015), CRR is the percentage or proportion of total deposit liabilities (demand, savings and time deposits) which deposit money banks and other financial institutions are required to keep with central bank in order to prevent shortage of cash in meeting the demand for cash by depositors (Udeh, 2015). Bawa, Akinniyi and Njarendy (2018) defined CRRs as taxes on the return on deposits both foreign and domestic on a bank balance sheet since other

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

resources that have similar risks and returns do not have cash required reserves. In other words, cash reserve ratio refers to the cash reserves or balances held by banks with the central bank and which the central bank has authority to vary according to the exigencies of the credit control. Such deposits with the central bank must not be less than a prescribed proportion of the banks' deposit liabilities. Cash reserve ratio is one of the most powerful instruments of monetary control that is used to increase or reduce the liquidity of banks. A change in the required ratio changes the ratio by which the banking system will expand deposit through the multiplier effect. Ojima and Ajudua (2024) stated that CRR may have an impact on DMBs profitability. This is because central bank pays zero interest on the amount commercial banks keeps with them as cash reserve. Deposit money banks earn their proceeds through lending of available funds at higher rates and paying lower rates of interest on deposits amount. An increase in CRR results in smaller amount of funds at the disposal of DMBs, increase in interest rate, decrease in liquidity and profitability in the system and vice versa.

2.1.4 Liquidity Ratio

Liquidity ratio is equally known as secondary reserve which ensures that banks are liquid at all times and also ensures that they are able to satisfy the liquidity needs of their customers, sustain the confidence of the public and ensures that the system is sound, safe and healthy

(Ojima & Ajudua, 2024). Olweny and Chiluwe (2022) defined liquidity ratio as the proportion of total deposits to be kept in specified liquid assets mainly to safeguard the ability of the banks to meet depositors' cash withdrawals and ensure confidence in the banking system. Liquidity ratio is used to increase or decrease cash availability of commercial banks, however, researchers have argued that the major use of the statutory liquidity ratio of banks is to float government securities, it therefore intends to direct commercial bank credit towards the public sector (Otalú, 2014). In sum, the central bank also imposes upon DMBs a minimum liquidity ratio, being varied according to the needs of the economic situation at hand. It is designed as such to enhance the ability of banks to meet cash withdrawals on them by their customers. According to Olaoye and Olaniyan (2022), such liquid ratio stands for the proportion of specified 'liquid' assets (such as cash, bills, and government securities) in the total assets of a bank. Thus, the central bank complements the use of OMO with liquidity ratio as one of the reserve requirements. Thus, liquidity ratio is an instrument for liquidity management and for prudential regulation. It refers to the proportion of banks' liquid assets to their total deposit liabilities. Any increase in this ratio, the ability of deposit money banks to create credits declines due to high liquidity requirement. However, with a decrease in liquidity ratio by the monetary authority, deposit money banks will be able to

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

expand their credit and make more profits (Nnanna, 2021).

2.1.5 Stock Market Prices

The stock market is a market which deals in long term loans (Udeorah, Oladosu & Odiche, 2025). It supplies firms with fixed and working capital and finance medium term and long term borrowings of the federal, states and local governments. Thus, the stock market encompasses of institutions and mechanisms through which medium term funds and long term funds are pooled and made available to corporate entities and governments. The stock market has been recognised as an institution that contributes to the socio-economic growth and development of emerging and developed economies. Donwa and Odia (2017) noted that this is made possible through some vital roles played, such as channeling resources, promoting reforms to modernize the financial sectors, financial intermediation capacity to link deficit to surplus sector of the economy, and a veritable tool in the mobilization and allocation of savings among competitive uses which are critical to the growth and efficiency of the economy. Stock markets are one of the relevant constituents of the financial system, which help firms or companies to raise capital by issuing their shares and also create an enabling environment which allows for trading of the shares. The stock market forms an integral part of financial system and serves important functions in an economy by means of providing liquidity for investors. There

is no generally acceptable definition of stock market as various authors have tried to define stock market but none of these definitions has been universally accepted.

However, stock market prices represent the current market value of a company's shares or stocks. In other words, it is the price at which a share of a company's stock can be bought or sold on a stock exchange. The market value here is the current which reflects the market's perception of the company's value based on factors like financial performance, industry trends, economic conditions and investor sentiments. Given that the focus of the study is on all the quoted companies in the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE), the All-Share Index was used a barometer for the prices of all quoted stocks in the NSE.

2.1.6 All-Share Index

In the financial lexicon, an index is a standardized way to track the performance of a group of stocks, assets, etc. It is a measure used to track the performance of equity or other assets. A basket of securities makes up the index used to track the performance of the basket. Put differently, an index is used to track a statistical measure of change in various security prices. According to Chen (2021), it typically refers to a statistical measure of change in a security market. A financial index produces a numeric score based on inputs such as a variety of asset prices. Thus, indexes measure the performance of a basket of securities intended to replicate a certain area of the market (Chen, 2021).

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

According to Hadden and Haug (2017), an index is a broad-based indicator that captures the entire market such as the Standard and Poor's 500 Index or Dow Jones Industrial Average (DJIA); or more specialized such as indexes that track a particular industry or segment such as the All-share index (ASI) which tracks only a class of stocks. The All-Share index is an indicator that shows the average prices of stocks

$$ASI = \frac{\sum Pa.Qa}{Pb.Qb} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where:

$$P = \text{Price of stocks}$$

This index (ASI) nonetheless is used in examining the previous high points and low points in the stock market. It is very important in predicting or determining the trends and reversals in the stock market. According, we have three movements with stocks which are: primary, secondary and minor movements. The primary movement is a long term movement of

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH)

This theory is also known as the stock market efficiency theory. The proponents of this theory are Working (1934), Kendall (1953), Roberts (1959), Osborne (1959), Rayner and Little (1966), and Fama (1970). The findings of these experts have now come to be known as the efficient market hypotheses. They believe that in an efficient market, security prices adjust so quickly to new information that they fully reflect

on the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE). Usually, it is used to determine the intensity of the Nigeria stock market generally. Indexes use base years for computational purposes and January 1, 1984 is the base year for Nigeria's All-share index (Nzotta, 2005). This index is given as:

$$Q = \text{Quantity of stocks}$$

$$a = \text{Current period}$$

$$b = \text{Base period}$$

upwards of one year which determines a company's term trend in stock market prices. Secondary movement is a short term movement of 0 - 12 months duration that is expected to counter the primary trend or to correct the error in the primary trend. Minor movement are daily or hourly movements in stock market prices (Daggiza, 2019).

available information about the security and that changes in security prices are independent since they have random movements (Lumby & Jones, 2023). Thus, this theory states that the price seen on an asset today is its true value, reflecting any data that could drive its price up or down. According to Fama (1970), this theory has three versions:

- **Weak Form:** states that current stock prices reflect all information available on past stock market prices.

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

➤ **Semi-Strong Form:** states that current stock market prices reflect all public available information.

2.2.2 Cyclical Theory

The proponents of this theory are Minsky (1977) and Kindleberger (1978). They focused on the various factors contributing to cyclical excess. According to them, the process leading to a crash in the stock market is usually started when some favorable events initiates a bidding-up of asset prices. Such a bidding-up is more likely to occur if a substantial period has elapsed since the last crash, and the motive of greed has gained strength relative to that of fear. Price rises lead to further buying in anticipation of a continuation of the current trend (bandwagon effects), and paper profits make it easier for speculators to finance additional purchases on margin (Haugen, 2021)). Eventually, when prices reach obviously overvalued levels, prices collapse, with disastrous effects on those investors, including financial intermediaries, whose portfolios were financed by borrowing.

2.2.3 Monetarist Theory

The proponents of this theory are Friedman and Schwartz (1963). They postulated that financial instability is not likely to arise or become serious in the absence of a disruption to the money supply. In their view, the basic cause of financial instability is to be found in monetary policy that either initiate financial instability or cause minor disruptions to have more far-reaching

➤ **Strong Form:** states that the current market price of a stock reflects all information, both public and non-public.

consequences. Thus, the central theme of the theory is that the money supply is the main driver of economic activity and inflation. The Monetarists believe that managing the growth rate of money supply can stabilize the economy, control inflation, and influence overall economic output (Udeorah, Oladosu & Odiche, 2025). Schwartz (1986), labels as “pseudo-financial crises”, those disturbances that are not accompanied by a significant decline in the quantity of money.

Theoretical Framework

The theory most suitable for this study is the Efficient Market Hypothesis that suggests three possible classes of efficiency for the capital market of every country. Given the development status of the stock market in Nigeria, the Nigerian stock market is said to be weak efficient where the prices of shares in the market reflect all information in past share prices, and also, share prices change irrespective of historical price fluctuations (Haugen, 2021). Put different, the performance of a company affects the price of the company's shares in the stock market. The share price of a company that has been doing well over time is always higher compared to a company that has not been doing well down the years. This explains why the prices of all shares

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

quoted in the Nigeria Stock Exchange are not the same.

2.3 Empirical Review

Udeorah, Oladosu and Odiche (2025) examined the impact of monetary policies on stock market development in Nigeria spanning between 1990 and 2023. The former was represented with interest rate, money supply, exchange rate and liquidity ratio while the latter was measured using market capitalization. They adopted descriptive and ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) techniques for data analysis. Results revealed that interest rate negatively and significantly impact stock market capitalization, while broad money supply and exchange rates exhibit positive and significant effects. Conversely, liquidity ratio has a negative but non-significant impact on market capitalization. They concluded that monetary policy serves as a critical stabilization tool influencing stock market development in Nigeria.

Tubotamuno and Oladosu (2024) examined the effects of monetary policy on Nigeria's stock market performance between 1985 and 2022. Monetary policy rate, money supply, lending rate, and treasury bills rate were used as proxies for monetary policy, while stock market capitalization served as a performance measure of the stock market. The major analytical tool was the Autoregressive Distributed Lag technique. The study postulated that monetary policy rate has negative and insignificant effects on stock market capitalization, while money

supply and treasury bills rate have positive and significant influences on stock market capitalization. Also, the study reported that lending rate has a negative but significant effect on stock market capitalization in Nigeria.

Anyanwu and Ohurogu (2024) examined the impact of interest rate and money supply on stock market liquidity in Nigeria by relying on annual time series data on the variables interest rate, broad money supply and stock market liquidity. The vector autoregression (VAR) estimation technique that also involves variance decomposition and impulse response function was adopted for data analysis. The study averred that interest rate has a significant negative impact on stock market liquidity while the money supply has a positive and significant impact on stock market liquidity in Nigeria.

Nugraha and Sari (2023) examined the effect of money supply and interest rate on stock prices in Indonesia and Malaysia between 2000 and 2020. They used the composite stock price index in analyzing macroeconomic effects on stock prices whereby money supply and interest rate served as macroeconomic variables. Findings revealed that both money supply and interest rate have significant influences on stock prices in Indonesia, while only interest rate has a direct influence on stock prices Malaysia.

Eriksson and Harja (2023) examined the relationship between money supply and stock prices in Sweden through a cointegration approach. Using monthly data from 1980 to

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

2022, the empirical analysis found no evidence of a long-run relationship. However, focusing on the time period after introducing the inflation target in 1993 of two percent inflation, the empirical analysis found evidence suggesting a cointegration relationship between the variables exists. The results also indicated a bidirectional causal relationship between the variables in the long run while in the short run, the causal relationship is unidirectional, running from money supply to stock prices.

Eghosa and Amenze (2022) investigated the influence of monetary policy instruments on stock market performance in Nigeria using monthly data between January 2010 and June 2019. The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) causality framework was used for data analysis and findings showed that monetary policy instruments of broad money supply and inflation rate have significant influences on All Share Index in the short run while broad money supply, inflation rate interest rate, exchange rate and market capitalization significantly influences stock market performance in the long run.

Ogbonna (2021) tried to ascertain the association between money supply and stock prices in Nigeria between 1985 and 2019 using broad money supply as a measure of money supply and marker capitalization as a proxy for stock prices. Given unit root analysis, the Johansen cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) analytical tools were

adopted for data analysis. Results revealed that there exists a long run relationship between the variables; and that money supply (M2) has a significant relationship with market capitalization of the Nigerian stock exchange. The study also revealed that there is a bi-directional causality between money supply and stock prices.

Omodero, Adetula and Adeyemo (2021) empirically examined stock market reactions to monetary policy modifications in Nigeria using annual time series data on All Share Indices, money supply, interest rate and exchange rate between 1998 and 2018. The study adopted Ordinary Least Square (OLS) multiple regression analytical technique and results showed that money supply has a significant favourable influence on All-Share Index. Also, interest rate has an insignificant effect on the Nigerian All Share Index.

John and Ezeabasili (2020) examined the effect of money supply on stock market performance in selected African countries for the period 1986 to 2018 using a simple regression model whereby stock market index was regressed on money supply for Nigeria, Ghana and South Africa. .Johansen cointegration test, Error Correction Model (ECM) and granger causality test were statistical tools employed. Results revealed the existence of a long-run relationship between money supply and stock market performance in Nigeria, South Africa and Ghana. Also, the results showed a unidirectional causal

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

relationship running from stock market performance to money supply in the selected countries.

Picha (2017) examined the effect of money supply on the stock market through the portfolio balance channel as a transmission mechanism of monetary policy. National flow of funds accounts, specifically assets from US households' portfolios, represented a key data source. Johansen's cointegration analytical technique was employed for data analysis and results showed that money supply exercises influence on valuation of S&P 500 index with 6 months lag. The impact is also distinguishable in the long run, whereas all observed asset classes can positively influence price of S&P 500.

Bissoon, Seetanah, Bhattu-Babajee, Gopy-Ramdhaney and Seetah (2016) investigated the impact of monetary policies on stock markets based on a sample of five open countries with growing stock market over the period 2004 to 2014. Using a random effect model for the panel regression coupled with a panel Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to study the short term and long term relationship between the variables, the findings revealed a negative relation between interest rate and stock return and a direct link between money supply and stock return. The results confirm that both in the short run and long run, monetary variables explain changes in stock return.

2.4 Gap in Literature

The novelty of this study is that it adopted a multiple regression model in estimating the cause-effect relationship between money supply and stock market performance in Nigeria. In essence, aside broad money supply (M₂), the model adopted considered money supply related variables like monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio as independent variables and stock market All Share Index as dependent variable.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the ex-post-facto research design. This is because emphasis was on determining the cause-effect relationship between money supply and stock market prices in Nigeria.

3.2 Sources of Data

This study only made use of secondary data. This data are on All-Share Index, broad money supply, monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin (for various years) was the source from which these data were collected.

3.3 Data Analytical Techniques

3.3.1 Descriptive Analysis

The data generated were first subjected to descriptive analysis, which involves summarizing and describing the basic features of the data like mean, maximum and minimum values, median, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis (Banks, 2020).

3.3.2 Stationarity/Unit Root Test

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

One feature of time series data is the presence of a unit root and this is capable of producing spurious, erroneous or fictitious results (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). To overcome this possibility, it between monetary policy and market capitalization in Nigeria. Accordingly, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) approach to unit root test was considered. This stationarity approach was applied in testing the null hypothesis of a unit root against the alternative

$$\Delta Q_t = P_0 + P_1 Q_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n h_i \Delta Q_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots\dots\dots$$

(1)

Where;

Q_t = Variable being investigated

Decision Rule: Accept H_0 (null hypothesis) and reject H_1 (alternative hypothesis) if the absolute value of ADF test statistic is less than the absolute critical value of ADF at 5% level of significance; otherwise, reject H_0 and accept H_1 .

3.3.3 ARDL Estimation

Given the unit root test, the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) analytical model estimation approach was adopted given its enormous benefits over other techniques. According Pesaran, Shin and Smith (2001), the ARDL technique is more efficient in small samples analysis, it has the tendency of combining linear variables with diverse orders of integration of $I(0)$ and $I(1)$, and it is less prone to autocorrelation problem (Pesaran, Shin & Smith,

is imperative to carry out a unit root test. Thus, this test was conducted in order to determine the most suitable analytical tool for the study in order to properly estimate the relationship hypothesis of no unit root at the conventional 5 percent level. For each of the variables included in the unit root model, it is expected to be $I(0)$ or $I(1)$, but not $I(2)$. According to Dickey and Fuller (2011), “the specification of the unit root model is provided as:

- P_i and h_i = Coefficients of the variable
- n = Lag length
- Δ = First Difference Operator
- μ_t = White noise”

2001). This technique as such gave short and long run estimates of the model.

3.3.4 Co-integration Test

The ARDL approach is also popular because of its unique in-built co-integration test mechanism called bounds test. Thus, the bounds test approach to co-integration was adopted to examine if long run relationship exists among the underlying variables of the study. In this test, the null hypothesis of no co-integration was tested against the alternative hypothesis of co-integration with the application of F-test (Brooks, 2010).

Decision Rule: If F-statistic is greater than the upper critical bound (UCB) value, reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1); and vice versa.

3.3.5 Diagnostic Test

Given the results of the ARDL estimates, there was need for diagnostic tests in order to ascertain the validity and reliability of the estimates

obtained (Ezem & Isu, 2018). This covered tests for the presence of serial correlation, heteroscedasticity and model suitability.

3.4 Model Specification

$$ALSI = F (BMS, MPR, LQR, CRR) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- ALSI = All-Share Index
- BMS = Broad Money Supply
- MPR = Monetary Policy Rate
- LQR = Liquidity Ratio
- CRR = Cash Reserve Ratio
- F = Functional relation

The model adopted for this study is functionally given as:

The ARDL version of the above functional model is formalized as:

$$ALSI_t = P_0 + \Pi_1 ALSI_{t-1} + \Pi_2 BMS_{t-1} + \Pi_3 MPR_{t-1} + \Pi_4 LQR_{t-1} + \Pi_5 CRR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m Z_1 \Delta ALSI_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m Z_2 \Delta BMS_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m Z_3 \Delta MPR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m Z_4 \Delta LQR_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m Z_5 CRR_{t-1} + e_{it} \dots (3)$$

Where;

- P_0 = Constant Parameter
- $\Pi_1 - \Pi_5$ = Long run multipliers
- $Z_1 - Z_5$ = Short run dynamic parameters of the regressors
- e_{it} = Random disturbance
- m = Optimal lag length
- Δ = First difference operator

3.4.1 A priori Expectations

$\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \Pi_3, \Pi_4 > 0$; this implies that the study expected broad money supply, monetary policy

rate, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio to have positive effects on stock market All-Share Index in Nigeria.

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 4.1: Data on All-Share Index (ALSI), Broad Money Supply (BMS), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Liquidity Ratio (LQR) and Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) in Nigeria (1990 -2023)

YEAR	ALSI (Index)	MPR (%)	CRR (%)	LQR (%)	BMS (₦'Billion)
1990	513.80	18.50	2.90	44.30	47.42
1991	783.00	15.50	2.90	38.60	75.40
1992	1107.60	17.50	4.40	29.10	111.11
1993	1543.80	26.00	6.00	42.20	165.34
1994	2205.00	13.50	5.70	48.50	230.29
1995	5092.20	13.50	5.80	33.10	289.09
1996	6992.10	13.50	7.50	43.10	345.85
1997	6440.50	13.50	7.80	40.20	413.28
1998	5672.70	13.50	8.30	46.80	488.15
1999	5266.40	18.00	11.70	61.00	628.95
2000	8111.00	14.00	9.80	64.10	878.46
2001	10963.10	20.50	10.80	52.90	1269.32
2002	12137.70	16.50	10.60	52.50	1505.96
2003	20128.94	15.00	10.00	50.90	1952.92
2004	23844.50	15.00	8.60	50.50	2131.82
2005	24085.80	13.00	9.70	50.20	2637.91
2006	33189.30	10.00	4.18	81.42	3797.91
2007	57990.20	9.50	2.80	41.56	5127.40
2008	31450.78	9.75	3.00	37.72	8643.43
2009	20827.17	6.00	1.30	26.39	9687.51
2010	24770.52	6.25	1.00	27.39	11101.46
2011	20730.63	12.00	8.00	42.02	12628.32

Opara Godstime Ikechukwu, *Ogu Callistus and Ojinnaka Henry Chigozie

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

2012	28078.81	12.00	12.00	49.72	15503.41
2013	41329.19	12.00	12.00	46.23	18743.07
2014	34657.15	13.00	20.00	38.27	20415.61
2015	28642.25	11.00	20.00	42.35	20885.52
2016	26874.62	14.00	22.50	45.95	24259.00
2017	38243.19	14.00	22.50	54.79	28604.47
2018	31430.50	14.00	22.50	65.04	29774.43
2019	26842.07	13.50	22.50	104.20	34257.90
2020	40270.72	11.50	27.50	67.60	36038.01
2021	42716.44	11.50	27.50	61.20	40370.41
2022	51251.06	16.50	27.50	54.93	48461.42
2023	74773.77	18.75	32.50	51.97	63512.40

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin (Various Issues)

4.2 Pre-Estimation Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive analysis

	ALSI	MPR	CRR	LQR	BMS
Mean	23204.60	13.88971	12.11118	49.61029	13087.73
Median	23965.15	13.50000	9.750000	47.65000	4462.655
Maximum	74773.77	26.00000	32.50000	104.2000	63512.40
Minimum	513.8000	6.000000	1.000000	26.39000	47.42000
Std. Dev.	18066.67	3.849533	8.886715	15.22638	16433.14
Skewness	0.736043	0.653449	0.746163	1.451541	1.343757
Kurtosis	3.310355	4.739458	2.336792	6.393818	4.112011
Jarque-Bera	3.206426	6.706071	3.778080	28.25666	11.98401
Probability	0.201249	0.034978	0.151217	0.000001	0.002499
Sum	788956.5	472.2500	411.7800	1686.750	444983.0
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.08E+10	489.0239	2606.132	7650.810	8.91E+09
Observations	34	34	34	34	34

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

Opara Godstime Ikechukwu, *Ogu Callistus and Ojinnaka Henry Chigozie

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

The table above contains the data characteristics of the variables used in the study. The table as such contains the mean, median, maximum value, minimum value, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis of the variables: ALSI, BMS, MPR, LQR and CRR. Thus, for the period covered, All-Share Index (ALSI), the dependent variable, averaged 23204.60 and varied from 513.80 to 74773.77 with a standard deviation of 18066.67. Monetary policy rate, cash reserve

ratio, liquidity ratio and broad money supply, the independent variables, have means of 13.89%, 12.11%, 49.61% and ₦13087.73 billion respectively. The table shows that all the variables are positively skewed (to the right). Finally, the variables ALSI, MPR, LQR and BMS are peaked (leptokurtic) relative to a normal distribution, while CRR is flat (platykurtic) relative to a normal distribution. This is because the kurtosis of is normal distribution is 3.

4.2.2 Stationarity/Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF Statistic	5% Critical Value	P-Value	Level of Integration
ALSI	-4.552488	-2.957110	0.0010	I(1)
BMS	-4.131554	-2.954021	0.0029	I(0)
MPR	-6.819191	-2.957110	0.0000	I(1)
LQR	-6.414987	-2.957110	0.0000	I(1)
CRR	-5.043603	-2.957110	0.0003	I(1)

Source: Extract from E-Views 10 Output (2025)

The table above shows that the variables ALSI, MPR, LQR and LQR were stationary at first difference while the variable BMS was stationary

at level. Hence, the variables had mixed order of integration. This informed the need to employ ARDL analytical technique.

4.3 ARDL Estimation/Analysis

4.3.1 Short Run Analysis

Dependent Variable: LOG_ALSI

Method: ARDL

Date: 09/08/25 Time: 10:47

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2023

Included observations: 31 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): LOG_MPR LOG_CRR

LOG_LQR LOG_BMS

Fixed regressors: C

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

Number of models evaluated: 2500

Selected Model: ARDL(2, 1, 0, 1, 3)

Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LOG_ALSI(-1)	0.920312	0.170421	5.400221	0.0000
LOG_ALSI(-2)	-0.504903	0.198704	-2.540978	0.0199
LOG_MPR	0.709036	0.379841	1.866665	0.0775
LOG_MPR(-1)	0.829751	0.349266	2.375704	0.0282
LOG_CRR	-0.760033	0.242919	-3.128753	0.0055
LOG_LQR	-0.708728	0.287263	-2.467178	0.0233
LOG_LQR(-1)	0.851548	0.216039	3.941633	0.0009
LOG_BMS	-0.002761	0.539426	-0.005119	0.9960
LOG_BMS(-1)	-2.168160	0.913573	-2.373276	0.0283
LOG_BMS(-2)	0.693994	0.773710	0.896969	0.3810
LOG_BMS(-3)	1.815665	0.705960	2.571909	0.0187
C	1.083685	1.518308	0.713745	0.4841
R-squared	0.964680	Mean dependent var		9.811504
Adjusted R-squared	0.944231	S.D. dependent var		0.957173
S.E. of regression	0.226040	Akaike info criterion		0.148440
Sum squared resid	0.970792	Schwarz criterion		0.703532
Log likelihood	9.699177	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.329386
F-statistic	47.17594	Durbin-Watson stat		1.908796
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

The table above contains short run ARDL results. It revealed that in the short run, one year lag of All-Share Index (ALSI) and monetary policy rate have direct effects on current ALSI while cash reserve ratio, liquidity ratio and broad money supply have negative effects on current year ALSI. The table equally revealed that the effects

of lagged ALSI, cash reserve ratio and liquidity ratio were significant at 5% level of significance. Also, from the table, the value of R^2 is 0.964680 and the p-value of F-statistic is 0.000000; which implies that all the explanatory variables of the model have a joint significant effect of about 96.5% on All-Share Index.

4.3.2 Bounds Cointegration Test

F-Bounds Test

Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	5.367826	10%	2.2	3.09
K	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

From the bounds test output above, the value of F-statistic (5.367826) exceeds the upper bound value at 5% level (3.49). This implies that there is cointegration between the variables. In other

words, there is a long run equilibrium relationship between money supply (and associated variables) and stock market prices in Nigeria.

4.3.3 ECM Estimation

ARDL Error Correction Regression

Dependent Variable: D(LOG_ALSI)

Selected Model: ARDL(2, 1, 0, 1, 3)

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Date: 09/08/25 Time: 11:17

Sample: 1990 2023

Included observations: 31

ECM Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LOG_ALSI(-1))	0.504903	0.140580	3.591572	0.0019
D(LOG_MPR)	0.709036	0.201349	3.521425	0.0023
D(LOG_LQR)	-0.708728	0.167691	-4.226383	0.0005
D(LOG_BMS)	-0.002761	0.378640	-0.007292	0.9943
D(LOG_BMS(-1))	-2.509659	0.561245	-4.471590	0.0003
D(LOG_BMS(-2))	-1.815665	0.427060	-4.251544	0.0004
CointEq(-1)*	-0.584591	0.091653	-6.378281	0.0000
R-squared	0.668851	Mean dependent var		0.135880
Adjusted R-squared	0.586063	S.D. dependent var		0.312601

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

S.E. of regression	0.201121	Akaike info criterion	-0.174140
Sum squared resid	0.970792	Schwarz criterion	0.149663
Log likelihood	9.699177	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-0.068589
Durbin-Watson stat	1.908796		

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

From the ECM result above, the cointegration equation has a coefficient of -0.584591 and a probability value of 0.0000. These are desired results which imply that in an event of any distortion to the established long run

equilibrium relationship between money supply (and related variables) and All-Share Index, the speed at which equilibrium can be restored is about 58.5% per annum.

4.4 Post Estimation (Diagnostic) Tests

Tests	Criterion	F-Statistic	P-Value
Serial Correlation	Breusch-Godfrey	1.635874	0.2240
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	1.105631	0.4078
RESET	Ramsey	2.836020	0.1094

Source: Extract from E-Views 10 Output (2025)

Given that all the probability values (0.2240, 0.4078 and 0.1094) above are greater than 0.05 (5%), it follows that there is no correlation between the errors of the model (serial correlation) and the errors of the model do not have constant variance (heteroscedasticity) but they are homoscedastic. However, Ramsey RESET test revealed that the model was well specified.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

Relying on short run results with respect to the specific objectives of the study, four major findings emanated from the study. Firstly, the study revealed that monetary policy rate has a positive insignificant effect on stock market All-Share Index (ALSI) in Nigeria. This implies that an increase in monetary policy rate will lead to

an increase in stock market ALSI and vice versa. This outcome was expected because an increase in monetary policy will increase lending rate of banks which will discourage investment in the money market and further encourage investment in the capital market (Eghosa & Amenze, 2022). However, the insignificant effect which runs contrary to expectation may be as a result of the underdeveloped nature of the Nigerian capital market that is saddled with high level of illiquidity (Bissoon, Seetana, Bhattu-Babajee, Gopy-Ramdhany & Seetah, 2016). Secondly, cash reserve ratio has negative and significant relationship with ALSI in Nigeria. In other words, an increase in CBN's primary reserve, cash reserve ratio, will reduce stock market prices (Anyanwu & Ohurogu, 2024).

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

This result which disagrees with the a priori expectation may be because Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria always find a way to maintain excess reserves which make monetary policy directives centered on cash reserve ratio to yield negative outcome with respect to the capital market (Udeorah Oladosu & Odiche, 2025).

Thirdly, liquidity ratio, a secondary reserve, has a negative but significant impact on stock market ALSI in the Nigeria. This aligns with the position expressed by Udeorah Oladosu & Odiche (2025). However, the first part of the result was not anticipated because all things being equal, an increase in liquidity ratio should push investment in the capital market up (Nugraha & Sari, 2023). This variation between actual and anticipated result could be attributed to the structural inefficiencies associated with the Nigerian system which makes the time lag between monetary policy formulation and execution wider than expected.

Finally, the effect of broad money supply on stock market ALSI is negative and insignificant. This result too was not anticipated because increase in money supply ordinarily should enhance the volume and value of investments the capital market can attract (Picha, 2017). Nevertheless, it is possible that the effect of money supply on ALSI was insignificant due to lack of transparency in the market as investors find it difficult to access their dividend at the end of the day (Tubotamuno & Oladosu, 2024; Omodero, Adetula & Adeyemo, 2021).

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

Monetary policy rate has positively and insignificantly affected stock market All-Share Index (ALSI) in Nigeria.

There is negative but significant relationship between cash reserve ratio and ALSI of the stock market in Nigeria.

Liquidity ratio has an inverse but significant impact on stock market ALSI in Nigeria.

Money supply (M2) has a negative insignificant effect on the ALSI of the Nigerian stock market.

There is a long run relationship between money supply (M2), monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio, cash reserve ratio and stock market ALSI in Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

Given the major findings that emanated from this study, it was concluded that money supply has a negative insignificant effect on stock market prices in Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Drastic measures should be adopted in order to ensure that the volume of money outside the banking system is significantly reduced in order for monetary policies to be more effective in Nigeria.

Deposit Money Banks should be encouraged to offer competitive deposit rates that will attract more funds into the banking system.

There is need for the Central Bank of Nigeria to offer better and competitive rates for treasury

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

bills and other money market instruments in order to keep funds in the banking system.

The operations of non-bank financial institutions and other non-traditional banking

References

Alalade, Y.S.A., Oseni, E., & Adekunle, O.A. (2020). Monetary policy and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Asian Social Science*, 16(11), 190–211.

Anyanwu, C.C., & Ohurogu, D.U. (2024). Stock market liquidity in Nigeria: The effects of interest rate and money supply. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 25(1) 114-130.

Bassey, G.E., & Ekong, U.M. (2019). Monetary policy and bank performance in Nigeria: A Vector Autoregression (VAR) approach. *International Journal of Economics & Finance Research & Applications*, 3(1), 11-34.

Bawa, A.B, Akinniyi, K.O., & Njarendy, P.I. (2018). Cash reserve ratio, money supply and the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Management*, 7(4), 9-18.

Bissoon, R., Seetanah, B., Bhattu-Babajee, R., Gopy-Ramdhany, N., & Seetah, K. (2016). Monetary policy impact on

institutions (branchless banks) should be properly scrutinize as their existence has a tendency to reduce the total credit of banks which can make monetary policy ineffective.

stock return: Evidence from growing stock markets. *Theoretical Economics Letters*, 6, 1186-1195.

DOI:

<http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/tel.2016.65112>

CBN (2023). Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin.

<https://www.cbn.gov.ng/documents/Statbulletin.asp>.

Chen, J. (2021). What is an Index? Examples, How It's Used, and How to Invest. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/index.asp>

Daggiza, R.T. (2019). Capital market and economic growth in Nigeria: An ARDL approach. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 9(1), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2021.1890367>

Donwa, P., & Odia, J. (2017). An empirical analysis of the impact of the Nigerian capital market on her socio-economic development. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 24(1), 135-142.

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

- Eghosa, L.G., & Amenze, O. (2022). Monetary policy and stock market performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 14(2), 336-352.
- Eriksson, L., & Harja, J. (2023). Money supply and stock prices: Analyzing the relationship in Sweden through a cointegration approach. *Master Thesis in Finance, School of Business, Örebro University, Sweden*.
- Fama, E.F. (1970). Efficient capital markets: A review of theory and empirical work. *Journal of Finance*, May, 383 - 417.
- Friedman, M., & Schwartz, A.J. (1963). Monetary trends: A review article. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 1, 293-305
- Hadden, O.I. & Haug, M.N. (2017). Exchange traded funds and capital market efficiency: A descriptive perspective. *Journal of Economics*, 11(6), 122-139.
- Haugen, R. (2021). *Modern investment theory*, (5th Ed.). New York: Prentice Hall.
- Hirota, S. (2023). Money supply, opinion dispersion, and stock prices. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 212, 1286–1310.
- Ibeabuchi, S.N. (2017) Overview of monetary policy in Nigeria. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 45(44), 15-37.
- John, E.I., & Ezeabasili, V.N. (2020). Money supply and stock market performance in Nigeria, South Africa and Ghana. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 3(1), 101-114.
- Kendall, R. (1953). The analysis of economic time series, Part 1: Prices. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, 96 (1), 11 – 25.
- Kindleberger, C.P. (1978). *Manias, Panics and Crashes: A History of Financial Crises*. New York: Basic Books.
- Lumby, S., & Jones, C. (2023). *Corporate finance theory and practice*, (7th Ed.). London: Thomson.
- Minsky, H.P. (1977). A theory of systemic fragility. *Hyman P. Minsky Archive*, 231. https://digitalcommons.bard.edu/hm_archive/231
- Nnanna, O.J. (2021). Monetary policy framework in Africa: The Nigerian experience. *Central Bank of Nigeria*, Garki, Abuja.

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

- Nugraha, G., & Sari, M. (2023). The effect of money supply and interest rate on stock price. *CEMJP*, 31(1), 233–240.
- Nzotta, S.M. (2005). *Corporate Financial Decisions (2nd Ed.)*. Owerri: Oliverson Industrial Publishing House.
- Ogbonna, U.G. (2021). Money supply and stock prices – A case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 4(10), 1893-1904. DOI: 10.47191/jefms/v4-i10-10
- Ojima, D., & Ajudua, E.I. (2024). Monetary policy and deposit money banks performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(2), 16–26.
- Olaoye, F.O., & Olaniyan, N. O. (2022). Monetary policy and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 12(3), 198–210.
- Olweny, T., & Chiluwe, M. (2022). The effect of monetary policy on private sector investment in Kenya. *Journal of Applied Finance & Banking*, 2(2), 239-287
- Omodero, C.O., Adetula, D.T., & Adeyemo, K. (2021). Stock market reaction to monetary policy modifications: Evidence from an emergent market. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 10(3), 59-66.
- Osborne, M. (1959). Brownian motion in the Stock Market. *Operations Research*, 7(2), 145 – 173.
- Otalu, A.M. (2014). Monetary policy and commercial banks performance in Nigeria: An assessment of credit creation role. *The International Journal of Business and Management*, 2(7), 45-51.
- Picha, V. (2017). Effect of money supply on the stock market. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 65(2), 465–472.
- Rayner, A.C., & Little, I.M.D. (1966). *Higgledy Piggledy Growth Again*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Roberts, H.V. (1959). Stock market ‘patterns’ and financial analysis: Methodological suggestions. *Journal of Finance*, 14(1), 1–10.

British International Journal of Applied Economics, Finance and Accounting

B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

Volume: 9; Issue: 6

November-December, 2025

ISSN 2234-2418

Impact Factor: 6.91

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

Schwartz, A.J. (1986). Real and pseudo financial crises”, in Forest Capie and Geoffrey Wood (eds), *Financial crises in the world banking system*. New York: St. Martin’s

performance of Islamic banking in Nigeria: A case study approach. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0017347>.

Tubotamuno, B., & Oladosu, I.O. (2024). Monetary policy and the performance of stock market in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 14(3), 1196-1208.

Udeh, S.N. (2015). Impact of monetary policy instruments on profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria: Zenith bank experience. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(10), 190-206.

Udeorah S., Oladosu I.O., & Odiche W. (2025). Interaction between monetary policies and stock market development in Nigeria: An econometrics analysis. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 13(1), 19-38.

Working, H. (1934). A random difference series for use in the analysis of time series. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 29(185), 11–24.

Yahaya, O.A., & Lamidi, Y. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial